

EOSC Symposium 2023

A summary for ELIXIR & Life Science stakeholders

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European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

The EC's ambition for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹ is to build a federated multi-disciplinary environment where European researchers, companies and citizens can publish, find and reuse data and services. Once available, the data and services can be used for research, innovation and educational purposes.

EOSC Symposium 2023 - Event overview

The EOSC Symposium 2023 took place 20-22 September in Madrid, Spain coinciding with the Spanish Presidency of the Council of the European Union. The event hosted close to 200 EOSC stakeholders representing the EOSC Tripartite, Research Infrastructures, ESFRI Science Clusters, NRENS, E-Infrastructures, and EOSC Member organisations. From the ELIXIR Research Infrastructure for life science data, over 20 members attended the three day event representing their EOSC projects, ELIXIR services, the ELIXIR Hub, EOSC Life Science Cluster and national Nodes. Additionally, ELIXIR hosted a booth which acted as a central point for fostering ELIXIR's engagement across the EOSC network and highlighted ELIXIR's EOSC Strategy².

EOSC Future Project - General Assembly & Project Extension

Preceding the main EOSC Symposium event, the EOSC Future project consortium³ met over two days on 18-19 September, 2023. Jonathan Tedds and Gavin Farrell from the ELIXIR Hub attended and represented ELIXIR, EOSC Life at the Technical Coordination Board level (JT) and Work Package 3.3 of the project which relates to the EOSC Interoperability Framework⁴. This was the final project meeting and initial closing point of the project. However, the EOSC Future project has been extended in a reduced capacity to continue over a six month extension period until March, 2024.

EOSC Future Project - General Assembly Highlights

Key items discussed during the EOSC Future meeting surrounded the preparation of EOSC Future extension activities:

- There will be a continuance of Work Packages: 1, 2, 5, 6, 7, and 10. These Work Packages will operate with a technical focus and focus on continuing support operations of the EOSC Core.
- The EOSC Future project outputs and results were discussed with regards to their handover to the EC and use by third parties. Related to this was project member handover planning around IP Management, licensing, documentation, and methods of best coordinating this alongside the upcoming EOSC Procurement⁵.
- Science use case projects from various Research Infrastructure's under WP6⁶ presented their outcomes.

¹https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

² <https://zenodo.org/records/7120997>

³ <https://eoscfuture.eu/about/consortium/>

⁴ <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-interoperability-framework/about-eosc-interoperability-framework-governance-eosc-if>

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/european-open-science-cloud-eosc-factsheet-procurement>

⁶ <https://eoscfuture.eu/ker/science-projects/>

- Newly funded EOSC projects of relevance to the outputs of EOSC Future were discussed such as the cross Science Cluster⁷ project EOSC OSCARS and EOSC Beyond (both detailed under section 'New EOSC projects').

EOSC Procurement

The EOSC procurement has been the process coordinated by the EC over the past year to determine the most suitable parties to operate the operational EOSC platform and related supporting elements. The procurement involved three 'lots' breaking down the elements required to operate the EOSC platform:

- Lot 1 – Core Federation Services for the EOSC EU Node
- Lot 2 – Exchange Infrastructure Services for the EOSC EU Node
- Lot 3 – Exchange Application Services for the EOSC EU Node

The successful winners of the procurement will operate these for 3 years between 2024 and 2027, with an ongoing monitoring of its success and possibility of extension beyond this point. The winning bidders were announced by the EC on 24 November, 2023 in a news release:

- <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/commission-announces-winners-eosc-procurement>

New EOSC projects

A number of new EOSC projects have been selected to receive funding by the EC and approved for a 2024 start. Several of these EOSC projects provided short overviews of their goals and intended contributions to the EOSC ecosystem during Symposium sessions. Some key EOSC projects of note for ELIXIR members to be aware of are:

OSCARS

- **Budget and coordinator**
€25 million budget, coordinated by CNRS-LAPP.
- **Project purpose**
The OSCARS project brings together ESFRI and other world-class Research Infrastructures organised in five "Science Clusters", that have cooperated over the last four years to raise the efficiency and productivity of researchers by providing open data services and infrastructures for discovering, accessing, and reusing data.
- **Key info for ELIXIR members**
A core component of this project for ELIXIR and Research Infrastructure stakeholders is the cascading funding open calls which will fund a broad range of science projects. The first call will open in March 2024, and a second in November 2024. Successful projects are to be awarded 100-250k euro. ELIXIR will support disseminating info for ELIXIR members on the open calls via the ELIXIR EOSC Focus Group⁸.

⁷ <https://science-clusters.eu/>

⁸ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/eosc>

EVERSE

- **Budget and coordinator**
€7.8 million budget, coordinated by CERTH.
- **Project purpose**
The EVERSE project aims to create a framework for research software and code excellence, collaboratively designed and championed by the research communities across five EOSC Science Clusters and national Research Software Expertise Centres. EVERSE will produce a framework for Research Software Quality and will set the foundations of a future Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence.
- **Key info for ELIXIR members**
The project includes several participating ELIXIR Node institutes and the Hub co-leading a number of the Work Packages as well as participating and contributing research software quality expertise to the project. A key output of the project for life sciences stakeholders will be the Research Software Quality Kit (RSQKit): an open knowledge base to gather and curate expertise that will contribute to high-quality software and code across different disciplines.

EOSC ENTRUST

- **Budget and coordinator**
€5 million budget, coordinated by ELIXIR Hub.
- **Project purpose**
The mission of EOSC-ENTRUST is to create a European network of trusted research environments for sensitive data and to drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis.
- **Key info for ELIXIR members**
The project is coordinated by the ELIXIR Hub and has several participating ELIXIR Node institutes co-leading Work Packages and contributing various trusted research environment (TRE) technologies and approaches to the project which enable processing sensitive data. ELIXIR and life science stakeholders should closely monitor project outputs for potential usage in their sensitive data analysis work as the project progresses.

EOSC Beyond

- **Budget and coordinator**
€10 million budget, coordinated by EGI.
- **Project purpose**

EOSC Beyond overall objective is to advance Open Science and innovation in research in the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) by providing new EOSC Core capabilities allowing scientific applications to find, compose and access multiple Open Science resources and offer them as integrated capabilities to researchers.

- **Key info for ELIXIR members**

The concept of EOSC Nodes will be explored in this project via pilots, a concept that will be important for ELIXIR to monitor and ensure strategic alignment to. Further, the EOSC Beyond project's use of the 'Simpl' technology approach to enable technical federation will also be important to monitor for ELIXIR service providers (detailed under section 'Data Spaces & Simpl + EOSC').

EOSC Nodes

The EOSC Nodes concept was formally discussed during a number of sessions during the Symposium in addition to an open community consultation. The exact definition of an EOSC Node is evolving but first insights on the concept can be found in GÉANT's EOSC Nodes position paper on behalf of the NREN community⁹. The EOSC community consultation session outcomes draft has been circulated by the EOSC Association since the event and a more mature copy is expected to be published in the coming months based on community feedback. EOSC Nodes are anticipated to be national, regional and thematic. Additionally, the EU EOSC Node concept is being developed. The EOSC Beyond project will explore facilitating federation with pilot EOSC Nodes. The pilot EOSC Nodes of the EOSC Beyond project will be:

National & Regional

- Germany (NFDI)
- Czech Republic (e-Infra CZ)
- NI4OS Southeast Europe (GRNET, IPB, UKIM)

Thematic

- Environmental (LifeWatch)
- Health and Food (METROFood-RI)
- Structural Biology (Instruct-ERIC)

⁹ <https://eosc.eu/news/2023/09/geant-publishes-eosc-nodes-position-paper-on-behalf-of-nren-community/>

EOSC: Governance and Financial Models, post-2027

During the Symposium, various sessions dealing with the governance, financial and legal entity models of EOSC were discussed in relation to the current EOSC Tripartite structure¹⁰. With regards to whether EOSC could exist for example as an EDIC¹¹, a Joint Undertaking¹² (such as EuroHPC JU) or other hybrid models were discussed for consideration. These discussions, prospective community consultations and outcomes will be closely followed by ELIXIR for any impact this may have.

Symposium sessions of note:

- Financial Models for EOSC post 2027 - <https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/financial-models-for-eosc-post-2027/>
- Governance models for EOSC post 2027 - <https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/governance-models-for-eosc-post-2027/>

EOSC Monitoring & the EOSC Observatory

A highlight session from the EOSC Symposium involved the monitoring of EOSC results, with a focus on how the adoption of Open Science and EOSC is progressing in participating European nations. The EOSC Observatory¹³ is a highlight open resource for accessing information on EOSC monitoring. This may be a resource of interest for ELIXIR Nodes looking at their nationally reported progress.

- EOSC Monitoring Results - <https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/eosc-monitoring-results/>

Data Spaces & Simpl + EOSC

Data Spaces

A synergistic area to EOSC which was highlighted across various Symposium sessions was the Data Spaces initiative. Full information on the Data Spaces initiative and the Data Spaces Support Centre can be found:

- <https://dataspaces.info/common-european-data-spaces/#page-content>
- <https://dssc.eu/>

ELIXIR Hub's Jonathan Tedds spoke at an EOSC Symposium session on behalf of ELIXIR Europe during a panel of stakeholders who are working to align their Research Infrastructures and project initiatives to the Data Spaces initiative. Most notable to ELIXIR is the developing European Health Data Space (EHDS) which is synergistic to the ELIXIR led Genomics Data Infrastructure project (GDI).

¹⁰ <https://eosc.eu/tripartite-collaboration/>

¹¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/edic>

¹² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/glossary/joint-undertakings.html>

¹³ <https://eoscobservatory.eosc-portal.eu/home>

Simpl

Simpl¹⁴ is the smart middleware that will enable cloud-to-edge federations and support all major data initiatives funded by the European Commission, such as common European data spaces. This may be important to monitor for ELIXIR bio-database stakeholders such as the Core Data Resources Forum and further for project stakeholders working with health data such as GDI, EOSC₄Cancer, and BY-COVID.

Symposium sessions of note:

- Data Spaces - <https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/data-spaces/>
- Data Spaces made Simpl - <https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/Simpl-and-the-data-spaces/>

EOSC Symposium 2024

Next year's EOSC Symposium event is anticipated to take place during the Autumn of 2024 in Berlin, Germany.

Event recording and slides

The majority of sessions have details on speakers, slides and recordings linked from the event programme site: <https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/programme/>

EOSC glossary of terms

<https://eosc-portal.eu/about/glossary>

ELIXIR EOSC Focus Group

<https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/eosc>

Official event photos

<https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/edition-2023-in-pictures/>

¹⁴

<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/simpl-streamlining-cloud-edge-federations-major-eu-data-spaces-updated-october-2023>

ELIXIR session highlights at the EOSC Symposium 2023 (Appendix 1)

- **Session: EOSC contribution to the EU Missions**
 - Nadim Rahman (EMBL-EBI) presented on BY-COVID & the COVID-19 Data Portal.
 - Salvador Capella-Gutierrez (ELIXIR Spain) presented on EOSC₄CANCER.
 - Marieke Willems (ELIXIR Hub), BY-COVID project manager, opened and introduced the session.
 - Recording and slides available:
<https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/eosc-contribution-to-the-eu-missions/>
- **Session: Semantic interoperability for data and metadata**
 - Susanna-Assunta Sansone (ELIXIR-UK) presented on FAIRsharing & RO-Crate
 - Wolmar Akerstrom (ELIXIR-SE), co-chair of the Semantic Interoperability Task Force, opened and introduced the session.
 - Recording and slides available:
<https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/semantic-interoperability-for-data-and-metadata/>
- **Session: European alignment on skills and training**
 - Celia van Gelder (ELIXIR-NL) was co-organiser of the session European alignment on skills and training and represented the ELIXIR perspective in the panel discussion.
 - Recording and slides available:
<https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/skills-training/>
- **Session: EOSC Interoperability**
 - Ludek Matyska (ELIXIR-CZ) presented the Life Science Login (AAI) service.
 - Jonathan Tedds (ELIXIR Hub), co-organiser and chair opened the session.
 - Recording and slides available:
<https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/eosc-interoperability/>
- **Session: Leveraging global data communities in regional initiatives and cross-border infrastructures**
 - Gavin Farrell (ELIXIR Hub) spoke on ELIXIR's Research Data Alliance Focus Group.
 - Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE) spoke on Data Together, ELIXIR, EOSC and alignments to global data communities.
 - Recording and slides available:
<https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/unconference-session-leveraging-global-data-communities-in-regional-initiatives-and-cross-border-infrastructures/>
- **Session: Data Spaces**
 - Jonathan Tedds (ELIXIR Hub) represented ELIXIR during the Data Spaces panel.
 - Recording and slides available:
<https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/data-spaces/>

Highlight Moments from ELIXIR (Appendix 2)

Members of ELIXIR at the ELIXIR EOSC Symposium booth.

Celia van Gelder (ELIXIR-NL) during the panel of the European alignment on skills and training session.

Marieke Willems (ELIXIR Hub) during the EOSC contribution to the EU Missions session.

Susanna-Assunta Sansone (ELIXIR-UK) during the Semantic interoperability for data and metadata session.

Jonathan Tedds (ELIXIR Hub) during the Data Spaces session

Ludek Matyska (ELIXIR-CZ), EOSC during the Interoperability session

